

were collected as the displacement solutions, and the rest as saturation extract.

The extracts were then recycled through soils three times, first allowing them to remain in contact with soil for about 30 min by keeping the drain tube closed. The final (fourth) extract was collected as the equilibrated saturation extract. To prevent further oxidation, the soil solutions were collected in flasks prefilled with N₂ gas.

We measured solution pH and Eh in an electrometric cell under N₂ environment. The recycled saturation extracts were representative of soil

Comparison of pH and Eh values^a of solutions from FC moist soils collected by 2 different methods.

Soil	Soil pH (1:1)	pH		Eh (V)	
		Displaced solution	Recycled saturation extract	Displaced solution	Recycled saturation extract
Luisiana clay	4.7	4.6 a	4.5 a	0.31 b	0.32 b
UK-1 clay loam	6.6	5.9 b	6.5 b	0.29 a	0.26 a
Pila loam	7.5	6.9 b	7.3 b	0.27 a	0.23 a

^aMean of 6 replications. In a row, treatment means of a given parameter having a common letter are not significantly different by DMRT at 5% level.

solutions; the displacement solutions were seriously diluted and altered by the displacing liquid (demineralized water, pH 5.38) (see table). During subsequent experiments, we

observed that it is necessary to recycle fast-draining soils three times; recycling once or twice seldom ensured equilibrium. □

Environment and its Influence

Forecasting tungro (RTV) epidemic in Tamil Nadu

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Sporadic RTV epidemics have been reported in several countries. In Tamil Nadu, the disease occurred in 1978, 1979, 1980, 1981, and 1984, but not in 1977, 1982, 1983, and 1985.

RTV can be controlled by timely application of insecticides to check the vector population. But in a nonepidemic year, preventive insecticides are wasted.

Only young rice plants are highly RTV susceptible; infection 45 d after sowing normally does not result in economic loss. A system to forecast possible epidemic RTV outbreak is needed.

We monitored light trap catches of the vector green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens* population for 9 yr (1977-85) and attempted to correlate weather factors with disease and vector incidence.

The vector population started increasing in mid-Aug, reached its peak between mid-Sep and early Oct, then

declined. Highly susceptible rice cultivar TN1 was planted at 2-wk intervals from Jul to Dec. RTV was severe in Sep and Oct; crops sown in the first 2 wk of Sep recorded maximum incidence. The period favorable to vector multiplication and RTV incidence was Sep-Oct.

The 9-yr weather data for Aug-Nov were analyzed critically. No significant difference in maximum and minimum temperatures was found between RTV epidemic and nonepidemic years. Rainfall and humidity patterns were also similar.

The data, however, revealed one important fact: when RTV occurred, the vector population increased (see table). This increase could be used to forecast a RTV epidemic. Vector populations during Aug cannot be taken as criteria, but population during the first 2 wk of Sep differentiated RTV epidemic and nonepidemic years. Total vector populations during Sep of epidemic and nonepidemic years were clearly distinguishable. Populations were more than 10⁵ in RTV epidemic years and around 10³ in nonepidemic years. □

RTV incidence and the vector population in Tamil Nadu during 1977-85.

Year	RTV incidence (%)	Green leafhopper ^a (no.)								Total during the season
		Aug		Sep		Oct		Nov		
		1-15	16-31	1-15	16-30	1-15	16-31	1-15	16-30	
1977	0	5	1,786	202	1,059	7,821	3,672	510	228	17,283
1978	18	175	167	3,639	20,882	92,783	143,150	7,537	584	268,917
1979	100	171	7,556	25,016	455,269	69,789	81,899	10,751	5,562	656,013
1980	40	555	4,114	49,310	53,005	148,940	21,072	148,940	21,072	447,008
1981	60	162	1,181	2,837	32,882	175,574	42,816	31,119	1,583	288,154
1982	0	1,330	2,544	1,494	2,544	7,449	1,733	343	118	16,555
1983	0	122	308	996	561	9,265	23,439	7,138	331	42,160
1984	70	1,223	1,995	106,115	15,308	33,543	6,102	168	66	164,510
1985	0	9	38	83	670	4,472	490	1,420	314	7,496
Mean		416	2,188	21,077	64,687	61,071	36,041	23,103	3,540	

^aPopulation was counted using a light trap.